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Social And Emotional Intelligence As Correlates Of Job Performance Among Private Schools Teachers In Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated social and emotional intelligence as correlate of job performance of private school teachers in Rivers State. The study adopted correlation design. The study was guided by three research questions and three hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. A sample of 578 teachers was drawn from 25 private schools. Simple and proportional stratified random sampling was used to draw the school and respondents. The instruments for data collection were Social Intelligence Competencies Scale (SICS), Emotional Intelligence scale (ELS) and Job Performance Scale (JPS) whose reliability was confirmed through Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment collected coefficient (r) and Z-test. From the findings, it was discovered that there was a significant positive relationship between the variables under study. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that employers of labour should include both social and emotional intelligence measures in their recruitment process so as to ascertain the applicant's level of possession of competency.

Keywords: Emotional, Intelligence, Job performance, Social

INTRODUCTION

It is an indisputable fact that the teacher is an important person and authority at every level of educational system. This is because apart from his/her inestimable primary role in curriculum implementation, his feeling or opinions about his/her job as well as the behaviour towards the students, management and outside the school are all issues of great concern. The opinion or feelings he has about his job as well as his behaviour pattern displayed in doing his job determine how dedicated, committed and effective he will be performing his job. The behaviour pattern of the teacher exert immense influence on students learning as well as on their overall achievement and orientation. An emotionally intelligent person is a person who can work in harmony with his /her thoughts and feeling, (Lana & Lopez-Zafra, 2010).

Job performance is a universal concept and has been described as the most dependent variable in organization and industrial psychology (Buelens, Kreitner, & Kinicki, 2013). Traditionally job performance is used to describe the extent to which workers carry out their roles assigned them. It has been conceptualized as the degree to which an individual executes his or her role with reference to certain specified standards set by the organization. Motowildo, Borman & Schmit (2015) asserted that job performance is the aggregate value of the discrete behavioural episodes to the organization that an individual performs over a standard interval of time in order to earn a living. This connotes that job

performance refers to the total value of acceptable behaviour exhibited by employees which conform to acceptable norms and standards that lead to realization of organizational goals and objectives.

Job performance is divided into two dimensions: task performance and contextual performance. Task performance refers to the behaviours, actions or activities that are directly linked with completion of the job and consists of execution of technical processes and maintenance and servicing of technical requirement. Contextual performance, on the other hand refers, to interpersonal behaviour or actions that benefit the organization. It includes activities such as; helping and cooperating with others, following organizational rules and procedures, and volunteering to carry out task and activities (Motowidlo et al. 2015& Nayyar, 2014). Each of these enquiries has made contributions in raising awareness about what contributes to overall performance in the workplace.

Goleman (2007) views social intelligence as interpersonal activities which results in successful relationship with people. It can be organized into two broad categories such as Social awareness, what we sense about others and social facility, what we do with that awareness. This suggests that social intelligence is the ability to process social skills that facilitate or produces desirable relationship with others. People who possess such social skills are able to interact freely both at the verbal and non-verbal levels. Thus, facilitate and maintain cordial relationship with others anywhere they find themselves. According to Erkman (2010) and Tubre and Collins (2015) Social intelligence is the ability to have and maintain positive relationship with others in any environment one finds himself. Shaka (2011) investigated the influence of social intelligence on job performance among high school teachers and discovered significant influence of social intelligence on job performance.

Emotional intelligences as defined by Goleman (2006), is the ability to identify, understand, use and manage ones and others emotional state effectively. This involves an intellectual process that leads to the use of emotional feelings to motivate, plan to achieve.

Emotional intelligence can be used as a term that refers to the ability to recognize, manage and influence one's and others emotions [Keating, Harper and Glew, 2013].

Therefore, emotional intelligence can basically be described as an interconnection between feelings and things.

Egbule [2009] and Agbe, Glenda, Ortese and Yusuf [2012] opined that emotional intelligence represents an ability to validly reason with emotions and to use emotion to enhance thought. It includes the ability to accurately perceive emotions, access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth. Bluelens et al [2013] added that emotional intelligence has strong correlation with high self –esteem, internal locus of control, self –efficacy, self – monitoring and career success. In essence, emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize the meanings of emotion, their relationships and to reason and solve problems on the basis occurrence.

Statement Of The Problem

Employees in every organization or institution are employed to perform certain duties assigned them irrespective of salary and non-salary conditions of service. With reference to teachers in private schools in Rivers state, personal experience and contact with most private school administrators and managers revealed that the private has been particularly vulnerable to high teacher turnover rate as records from some schools, show that about 30% of teachers are relieved of their appointments by the end of each term which about 50% suffer termination of appointment by the end of each session. Out of twenty five schools visited, only about 10% of teachers have remained in the same school for about three years, only about two percent of teachers have remained four years while majority of teachers have worked less than a year. Further enquiries revealed low performance as major reason for termination. Low performance results in withdrawal of wards by parents which invariably result in loss of income to the school established with the aim of maximizing profit. The foregoing reveals that private school teachers work under similar conditions of salary and non –salary conditions but they have varying levels of performance in their teaching job which determines their continuous stay on the job or termination of appointment. Sequel to the above mentioned problems, it is likely that apart from salary and non- salary conditions of

service, other personal aspects of the individual teacher’s life including social and emotional intelligence may influence performance. Therefore, this present study sought to investigate the social and emotional intelligence as correlates of job performance among private schools teachers in Rivers state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the conduct of the study

1. What is the relationship between teachers’ social intelligence and their job performance?
2. How does teachers’ emotional intelligence relates to their level of job performance?
3. What is the relationship between Teachers’ social and emotional intelligence

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.5 level of significance guided the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers’ social intelligence and their job performance.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers’ emotional intelligence and their job performance
3. There is no significant relationship between teachers’ social and emotional intelligence

METHODOLOGY

The design used for the study was correlational design. Because it is concerned with determining the degree of relationship between two or more variables, indicate the direction and magnitude of relationship between the variables and also used in testing hypothesis of significance. (Agbe et al.2012). A sample of 578 teachers was drawn from populations of teachers in private schools in Rivers State.

Three instruments were used for the study respectively named social intelligence competencies scale (SICS) consists of 12 items, emotional intelligence scale consist of 30 items and Job performance scale (JPS) made up of 16 items were adapted. The reliability of the instruments was determined through the test retest method, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Thus, the reliability of the Social Intelligence Competencies Scale Was. 79, Emotional intelligence Scales. 78 while Job performance scale was 81.

Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (r) was employed to determine the direction and magnitude of relationship between the dependent and independent variables while hypotheses were tested using z-test to find out the significance of R-values.

FINDINGS

Research question 1: *What is the relationship between teachers’ social intelligence and their job performance?*

Hypothesis I: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ social intelligence and their job performance Table I: Pearson’s correlation and z-test analysis of teachers’ social intelligence and their job performance.

Variable	N	X	SD	df	r	zrcal	zrcrit	Result
Social Intelligence	578	31.19	5.30	577	.861	64.6	1.96	sig.
Job Performance			42.99		7.55			

(P>0.05)

Table I reveals that the correlation coefficient (r-value) between teachers’ social intelligence and their job performance is .861. This indicates that there is a high positive relationship between teachers’ social intelligence and their job performance. Also, the zrcal value of 64.6 is greater the the critical z-value of 1.96 required for significance at 0.05 level for a two-tailed test. The result therefore is that there is significant relationship between social intelligence and job performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected.

Research question 2: *How does teachers' emotional intelligence relates to their job performance?*

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence and their job performance.

Table 2: Pearson's correlation and z-test analysis of teachers' emotional intelligence and their job performance.

Variable	N	X	SD	df	r	zrcal	zrcrit	Result
Emotional Intelligence	578	81.3	14.48	577	.824	99.06	1.96	sig
Job performance			42.99	7.55				

(P>0.05)

Table 2 shows that the correlation coefficient (r-value) between teachers' emotional intelligence and their job performance is .824. this indicates that there is a high positive relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence and their job performance. It also shows that the zrcal value of 99.06 is greater than the critical z-value of 1.96 required for significance at 0.5 level for a two-tailed test. The result therefore is that there is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected.

Research Question 3: *what is the relationship between teachers' social and emotional intelligence?*

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between teacher's social and emotional intelligence.

Table 3: Pearson's correlation and z-test analysis of Teachers' social and emotinal intelligence.

Variable	N	X	SD	df	r	zrcal	zrcrit	Result
Social	578	31.18	5.30	577	.799	81.59	1.96	sig
Emotional Intelligence			81.31	14.48				

(P>0.05)

Table 3 shows that the correlation coefficient(R-value) between teachers' social and emotional intelligence is .799. this indicates that there is a high positive relationship between Teachers' social and emotional intelligence. Furthermore, the zrcal value of 81.59 is greater than the critical z-value of 1.96 required for significance at 0.05 level for a two-tailed test. The result therefore is that there is significant relationship between social and emotional intelligence of teachers

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between teachers' social intelligence and their job performance. The finding agrees with Heri (2017), Pamos (2011) and Ajad (2011) who find significant positive relationship between social Intelligence and job performance. In contrast, the study disagrees with Cobb (2014) and Walsh (2009) whose reports shows insignificant relationship between social intelligence and job performance among workers in the banking sectors. They opined that workers with high social intelligence may possess inter- personal effectiveness which enhances success in work place. The finding on the relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence and their job performance was in consonance with the study of Jackie (2010) and Agbe etal (2012). However, the study disagrees with the finding of Walsh (2009) and Cobb (2014).

The findings between the relationship between teachers' social and emotional intelligence in private school in Rivers State has significant positive relationship.

The finding of the study of disagrees with the studies of Walsh (2009) and Cobb (2014) who found no significant relationship between social and emotional intelligence.

CONCLUSION

The finding of the study has indicated that social and emotional intelligence plays a significant role in enhancing teacher's performance. Therefore, the issues of being socially and emotionally intelligence

stable should be taken into cognizance in order to produce quality teachers since they played a paramount role in curriculum implementation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- Employers of labour should include both social and emotional intelligence measures in their recruitment process so as to ascertain the applicant's level of possession of competency.
- In – service training should be subsequently organized by the school authorities in order to continuously improve the levels of teacher's social and emotional intelligence.
- Counseling units should also be established in all primary and secondary school in the state qualified Guidance Counselors and educational psychologists be posted to take charge of the units to carry out training programmes.

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